

Review Article

Recent advances in graphene-based electrochemical biosensors for major non-communicable diseases

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Non-communicable diseases, including cancer, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, and neurological disorders, represent a growing global health challenge, driving an urgent need for rapid, sensitive, and affordable diagnostic technologies. Graphene-based materials, with their exceptional physicochemical properties, offer transformative potential for the development of next-generation electrochemical biosensors. This review highlights recent advancements in the use of graphene derivatives (such as reduced graphene oxide, graphene quantum dots, laser-induced graphene, and covalently functionalized graphene) for the electrochemical detection of key biomarkers associated with major non-communicable diseases. We critically analyze strategies for enhancing biosensor performance, discuss innovations in biomarker recognition and real-sample validation, and underscore emerging trends toward wearable, minimally invasive platforms. Particular emphasis is placed on the challenges of selectivity, stability, and clinical translation, as well as on the need for reproducible material synthesis and device standardization. By bridging material science with biomedical applications, graphene-based biosensors are poised to enable earlier diagnosis, continuous monitoring, and improved management of non-communicable diseases, ultimately contributing to the advancement of global healthcare.

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Introduction

Worldwide, over 41 million people die each year from five non-communicable diseases (NCDs), such as cancer, cardiovascular disease, chronic respiratory disease, mental illness, and diabetes [1]. According to the World Economic Forum's (WEF) evaluation, these five chronic diseases could have a collective global economic effect of \$47 trillion by 2030 [2]. For individuals, communities, and health systems, treatment of NCDs represents a huge financial and social burden [3]. In light of an aging population, the situation is expected to become even more challenging in the future. The challenges associated with NCDs may also be mitigated by efficient and cheap diagnostic tools, enabling fast, affordable, and early diagnosis, which is needed for efficient treatment of NCDs and reduction of associated costs. Electrochemical biosensors have become reliable diagnostic instruments with notable benefits in terms of real-time monitoring, speed, sensitivity, cost-effectiveness, and adaptability. They provide affordable and accessible healthcare tools on a global scale as the healthcare system transitions to an autonomous and patient-centric model [4]. In this respect, glucometers represent the flagship application with well-demonstrated clinical benefits for diabetes treatment. However, electrochemical biosensors still face challenges related mostly to selectivity, long-term stability,

and performance in complex biological environments. Recent years have witnessed significant progress in healthcare diagnostics, partly due to the emergence of new materials, including graphene (Gr) [5], that can enhance the sensitivity, selectivity, and efficiency of biosensors due to their remarkable physicochemical properties. Compared to other nanomaterials such as carbon nanotubes, metal nanoparticles, metal oxides, MXenes, and quantum dots, Gr and its derivatives exhibit an exceptional combination of high intrinsic charge carrier mobility, stability, bio-compatibility, large specific surface area, and versatile surface functionalization [6–8]. These properties contribute to faster electron transfer, stable biomolecule immobilization, and enhanced sensitivity and miniaturization in electrochemical biosensors [9].

Gr is a single layer of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms arranged in a two-dimensional hexagonal lattice. It allows efficient transduction of biological signals to a measurable electrical output [10]. However, one of the major challenges associated with pristine Gr in biosensing is restacking and poor dispersion in biological media [11]. To mitigate this limit, Gr can be functionalized using non-covalent approaches, typically by large functionalized polyaromatic hydrocarbons, e.g., pyrenebutyric acid [12], which stacks on the Gr surface. Non-covalent Gr functionalization can also enhance its interfacial interaction at the cellular level and increase its biocompatibility [13]. This ensures the sensing material interacts safely and effectively with the biological system. The non-covalent interactions are weaker than covalent interactions, which involve a covalent chemical bond. Therefore, the non-covalent assemblies can disintegrate, and the functional groups

may leak into the system [14]. This calls for either the covalent functionalization of Gr or the utilization of other nanomaterials in electrochemical biosensors. It was shown that various Gr-derived materials, i.e., reduced graphene oxide (rGO), laser-induced graphene (LIG), graphene quantum dots (GQDs), and covalently functionalized Gr, including Gr acid and N-doped Gr acid, can function as efficient transducing materials in electrochemical biosensors. Covalently functionalized Gr enables the efficient binding of the target analyte to a biorecognition element [15,16]. In the areas of oncology and cardiology, members of the Gr family have been shown to effectively detect biomarkers such as DNA, proteins, mRNA, troponin, BNP, and myoglobin [17–19]. Incorporation of Gr-based materials into point-of-care diagnostics, such as diabetes monitoring and neurological disease detection, promises consistency and high accuracy [20]. This review synthesizes the recent advancements in Gr-based electrochemical biosensors for major NCDs. It provides an overview of current challenges and prospects of this field, highlighting future potential to transform modern healthcare diagnostics. To emphasize the growing research interest in this area, Figure 1 shows the annual number of publications from 2010 to 2025 on Gr-based electrochemical biosensors related to NCDs, based on literature database analysis.

Graphene-based electrochemical biosensor for monitoring NCDs

An electrochemical biosensor is an integrated device consisting of two main components: a bioreceptor and a transducer. Selecting an appropriate bioreceptor for the sensor determines the level of

Figure 1

Annual publication trends (2010–2025) in Gr-based electrochemical biosensor research for major non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including cancer, cardiovascular, neurological disorders, and diabetes. Data retrieved from a keyword-based search on Scopus.

selectivity for a specific analyte and enables accurate detection [20]. The transducer serves as a bidirectional interface that critically influences the sensor's sensitivity, enabling the system to both respond to an applied potential and convert target-binding events into quantifiable electrochemical signals. Based on the transduction mode, the electrochemical biosensor can operate using amperometric, potentiometric, impedimetric, or voltametric methods [21,22].

The method used to deposit Gr significantly affects the electrode's morphological, electrical, and interfacial properties, thereby affecting the overall performance of the biosensor. Common strategies include drop-casting, which is easy to implement but often produces non-uniform films [23]. Electrochemical deposition enables controlled and adherent film growth, while dip-coating and spin-coating techniques offer improved control over the thickness, uniformity, and morphology of Gr layers [9,24,25]. LIG directly produces porous, high-conductivity Gr on flexible substrates [26]. Screen-printing is widely employed in low-cost, scalable sensor manufacturing. More advanced deposition techniques include inkjet printing, which provides scalable and precise patterning suitable for miniaturized sensors [8] and 3D printing, which enables customizable designs, rapid prototyping, and precise control over the structural architecture of biosensors [27]. Among these, inkjet printing, 3D printing and LIG are increasingly gaining attention for their ability to enable reproducible, low-cost, and wearable biosensor platforms. The incorporation of Gr-based material with the transducer can remarkably improve biosensor's physicochemical properties, such as the electroactive surface area and electrical conductivity [28]. The ultrathin 2D structure of Gr, along with conjugated composite material, plays an important role in detecting various biomarkers associated with NCDs. The following chapters will discuss the recent advances from the past two years in Gr-based electrochemical sensors for the detection of major NCDs, including cancer, cardiovascular disease, neurological disorders, and diabetes.

Cancer detection

Cancer is one of the most common NCDs and the predominant cause of mortality worldwide [29]. According to the WHO's International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), the number of cancer cases globally is expected to rise significantly, with an estimated 77 % increase by 2050 to reach over 35 million new cases each year [30]. Based on estimates, cancer is the primary cause of death for individuals under the age of 70 in 112 out of 183 nations [31]. Although conventional diagnostic tools for cancer detection, such as biopsy, imaging, CT scan, and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), are precise, they are often time-consuming and expensive [32]. Specific chemicals are either released into the bloodstream in reaction to malignancy

or produced by cancer cells, such as carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA), one of the principal biomarkers of colorectal cancer, and other malignancies in the ovary, lung, and liver [33–35]. Electrochemical detection of such cancer-related biomarkers at low concentrations provides evidence of the malignancy stage and is useful for the early detection of this disease. In recent times, Gr-based electrochemical biosensors have been used as noninvasive instruments to detect various types of cancer biomarkers at low concentrations [18]. Tao *et al.* [36] developed a graphene oxide (GO) nanocomposite-based biosensor for the electrochemical determination of CEA to detect colorectal cancer. They used GO and poly(propylene imine) (PPI) dendrimer nanocomposites as a stable platform for the immobilization of capturing target molecules, anti-CEA. The differential pulse voltammetry (DPV) technique was used to evaluate the response of GO-anti CEA, PPI, BSA, and GCE at a scanning rate of 100 mV s^{-1} in 0.1 M KCl solution with 2 mM $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$. The linear response of the sensor was calibrated in the range of $0.001\text{--}2000 \text{ ng mL}^{-1}$, and the limit of detection (LOD) was recorded as 0.3 pg mL^{-1} . Measurements of CEA were conducted in human serum samples, yielding relative standard deviation values ranging from 4.49 % to 5.04 % and recovery rates of 90.00 %–99.98 %. These characteristics demonstrate the method's efficacy and accuracy for clinical testing of CEA in real-world samples. Shankar *et al.* [37] proposed a zirconium trisulfide-rGO-modified biosensor for the detection of lung cancer biomarker cytoskeleton-associated protein 4 (CKAP4). In this work, morphology of the Gr film played a pivotal role in governing sensor performance. The dip-coating technique enabled a homogeneous and conformal deposition of ZrS_3 nanodots over the wrinkled and high-surface-area structure of the rGO nanosheets, enhancing the electroactive surface and facilitating effective electron transfer. The combined effect of the rGO morphology, uniform distribution of ZrS_3 nanodots, and the conducting polymer matrix significantly enhanced the redox behavior of disulfide groups. The method processed real serum samples obtained from patients suffering from lung cancer. The broad linear detection range of this sensor was $6.25\text{--}800 \text{ pg mL}^{-1}$, and the LOD was 6.25 pg mL^{-1} . This biosensing electrode also displayed a good storage life of 42 days. The electrochemical response accuracy tested against ELISA using real serum samples from cancer patients supported the method as a candidate for clinical application. Yen *et al.* [38] employed a laser-scribing deposition technique to fabricate laser-scribed graphene (LSG) directly onto the electrode surface. This method produced a flakes like porous structure with enhanced surface area and conductivity, which facilitated the simultaneous electrochemical detection of liver cancer biomarkers – carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and α -fetoprotein (AFP). The controlled morphology provided more accessible active sites for biomolecule

immobilization and facilitated faster electron transfer kinetics. Aptamers were integrated onto LSG surface through a stepwise surface modification strategy involving APTES silanization followed by succinic anhydride treatment to introduce carboxyl groups. The aptamers were then immobilized via amine–carboxyl interactions, and BSA was applied to block non-specific sites, ensuring selective and stable bio-functionalization of the LSG surface. Cyclic voltammetry was performed in 0.1 M PBS for the activation of the LSG electrode to ensure high electron density and generate new active sites. A DPV technique was used for the detection of CEA and AFP in PBS (pH 7.4), and the detection range was shown to span from 0.75 ng mL^{-1} to 100 ng mL^{-1} . The LOD was found to be 13.68 pg mL^{-1} for AFP and 50.66 pg mL^{-1} for CEA. Along with the standard analytical results, the practical utility of this research is that the electrode material is very flexible, small in size, low-cost, and easy to fabricate, making it a promising candidate for point-of-care devices for the detection of important cancer biomarkers. Kivrak et al. [39] demonstrated the detection of ovarian cancer-related mRNA based on carboxylate GO. The presence of carboxyl groups on GO enhances the hydrophilicity and the high affinity for targeting mRNA. Two mRNA biomarkers belonging to ovarian cancer, mir-141 and mir-200c, were detected by the square wave voltammetry (SWV) technique in Tris–HCl. The detection limits were recorded for mir-141 and mir-200c as 0.029 pM and 0.026 pM , respectively. Notably, Gr acid, equipped with carboxyl groups and synthesized by a highly reproducible process [40], could also provide a useful platform for detecting mRNA. Another distinct approach for mRNA detection was developed by Barman et al. [41] (Figure 2a) who used peptide nucleic acid (PNA) on a LIG electrode for biomimetic probe integration. The single-step fabrication and probe functionalization relied on π – π stacking interactions, enabling stable and selective detection of complementary nucleic acid sequences. The sensor's readout was measured using a smartphone with a very low detection limit of 0.6 aM . As proof of concept, this study successfully demonstrated electrochemical detection of a promising prostate cancer biomarker, hsa-mir-141, from both buffer and diluted serum samples. This detection strategy offers potential for applications in liquid biopsy and point-of-care diagnosis.

Cardiovascular disease detection

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) encompass a range of disorders affecting the heart and blood vessels and represent the leading cause of mortality in developed nations [45]. Their primary cause is an accumulation of fatty plaques, such as cholesterol and lipids, within the arterial walls [19], leading to the progressive narrowing of the arteries, which restricts oxygen-rich blood flow to the heart and substantially increases the risk of

myocardial infarction, heart failure, and stroke [46]. Numerous cardiac biomarkers, such as myoglobin and troponin, are released when blood flow is restricted in the vascular tissue surrounding blood cells [47]. Currently, several methods of testing CVDs, including echocardiography, electrocardiography (ECG), and angiography, are used. However, electrocardiography is the most reliable technique for identifying acute CVDs in a single test. Although the early diagnosis of CVD using echocardiogram has certain limitations, the quick detection of cardiac biomarkers is a promising way to prevent CVDs. Recently, researchers have been developing Gr-based electrochemical sensors for the early detection of various cardiac biomarkers. Torati et al. [48] created an advanced LIG-based sensor for the detection of C-reactive protein (CRP), a critical biomarker for forecasting CVDs. The LIG was incorporated due to its ideal property of bimolecular immobilization and signal transduction. Two-dimensional metal carbide MXene with gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) composite was used in the working area of the LIG-electrode. To detect the CRP antigen electrochemically, DPV technique was used, and the detection range and LOD of this sensor were reported as 10 pg mL^{-1} to $10 \text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ and 1.45 pg mL^{-1} . Vasudevan et al. [42] established lignin-scribed Gr with N-GQD for the detection of troponin-1 (Figure 2b), an important cardiac biomarker for CVDs. LSG was combined with nitrogen-doped Gr quantum dots (N-GQDs) and silver nanoparticles to develop this sensor. The composite structure helped to overcome the limitations of the individual materials. N-GQDs were stabilized on LSG through π – π stacking to improve the sensor's stability and sensitivity. Impedimetric analysis was done, and this sensor could detect up to 1 fM with a small sample volume of $10 \text{ }\mu\text{L}$. Arumugasamy et al. [49] used GQDs as a bio-receptor for the detection of cardiac troponin-1. Antibodies were covalently immobilized onto GQDs using EDC/NHS chemistry to construct a cardiac troponin-1 immunosensor, where BSA was applied as a blocking layer to reduce non-specific interactions and enhance signal specificity. Voltammetric and amperometric analysis were successfully used for the calibration of the sensor in PBS medium. The LOD and sensitivity were recorded for this sensor as 29 pM and $15.8 \text{ }\mu\text{A/nM}$. Recently, a Gr-gold nanohybrid self-assembly with GO nanosheet was used for the fabrication of a label-free aptasensor for cardiac troponin-1 by Kakkar et al. [50] The alternative approach of using a hybrid biofunctionalized Gr-based nanocomposite with aptamers led to an increase in the sensitivity for the detection of troponin-1. SWV technique was used for the sensing measurements of troponin-1, and the linear range of this sensor recorded 0.001 – 1000 pg mL^{-1} with a sensitivity of 0.001 pg mL^{-1} . The ultrasensitive level-free detection of troponin-1 was achieved based on conformational switching of the aptamer. The developed sensor can be utilized for regular periodic

Figure 2

Gr-based electrochemical biosensors for the detection of various NCDs. **(a)** Single-step PNA functionalization of LIG electrode for mRNA-based prostate cancer detection from serum samples. Adapted under the terms of the CC-BY license from the American Chemical Society [41]. **(b)** Lignin-derived nanoparticle intercalation on N-GQDs for electrochemical sensing of cardiac biomarker troponin-1. Adapted with permission from Elsevier [42]. **(c)** LIG-AuNPs-based biosensor for impedimetric detection of Parkinson's disease biomarker phosphorylated α -Syn. Adapted with permission from Elsevier [43]. **(d)** MXene-rGO-composite-based bifunctional electrochemical sensor for simultaneous detection of glucose and pH. Adapted with permission from Ref. [44]. Copyright (2024) American Chemical Society.

monitoring of troponin-1 for early diagnosis of myocardial disease.

Neurological disease detection

Globally, neurological problems are the primary cause of disability and contribute significantly to the burden of NCDs. Neurological diseases affect nearly 3.4 billion individuals, roughly 43 % of the world's population [51]. Neurotransmitters (NTs) are crucial for neural communication in the central nervous system and regulate vital processes like memory, mood, cognition, and sleep [52]. Accurate detection of NTs like dopamine (DA), serotonin (5-HT), adrenaline, and other biomarkers associated with neurological disorders is challenging due to their strong interfering environment and the necessity for specificity in real samples [53]. Dopamine is pivotal in regulating mood, cognition, and physiological functions, with abnormal levels linked to disorders such as Parkinson's disease, schizophrenia, and ADHD [54]. Typical dopamine concentrations in the extracellular fluid of the central nervous system range between 0.01 and 1 μM . Combining Gr derivatives with catalytic nanoparticles or heteroatom doping (B, N) has emerged as an effective strategy to significantly enhance the sensitivity and selectivity of the electrochemical biosensor. Recently, Ai et al. [55] studied Gr coupled with Cu_x^{2-}S nanostructures and achieved ultra-low dopamine detection limits down to 100 fM, with a broad linear range (100 fM to 100 μM). This sensor demonstrated exceptional selectivity in the presence of common interferents such as uric acid and ascorbic acid, verified through tests in diluted rat serum samples with dopamine concentrations below 100 pM. $\text{Cu}_x^{2-}\text{S}/\text{Gr}$ showed minimal signal loss during use of 9 days, supporting its suitability for long-term monitoring. Similarly, another $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2/\text{p-rGO}$ composite developed by Yu et al. [56] provides an extensive linear detection range of dopamine from 100 fM to 450 μM with an exceptionally low LOD of 78 pM. As validation on real samples is crucial, Mondal et al. [57] developed the electrochemical platform of NiO_x paired with partially reduced GO on fluorine-doped tin oxide substrates that successfully detects dopamine with an LOD of 22.0 nM, using human urine samples. Low serotonin (5-hydroxytryptamine, 5-HT) levels are implicated in various medical conditions, including depression, anxiety, sexual dysfunction, Parkinson's disease, and Alzheimer's disease. Recent advances by Liu et al. [58] include the development of Gr electrodes co-doped with boron and nitrogen, capable of detecting serotonin concentrations between 9 and 266 nM. These electrodes demonstrated high sensitivity and stability across diverse biological samples, including gastric juice, intestinal fluid, and blood. The B, N co-doping strategy results in a good fouling resistance, resulting in excellent repeatability, reproducibility, and one-month long-term stability during serotonin monitoring.

Additionally, increasing boron and nitrogen doping levels further enhanced the electrochemical kinetics of these Gr electrodes. In 2025, for the application in Parkinson's disease (PD), Jeong et al. [43] demonstrated that measuring phosphorylated α -synuclein (α -Syn) in blood provides diagnostic insights (Figure 2c). A novel biosensor using gold nanoparticles on LIG (LIG-AuNPs) effectively distinguishes PD patients from healthy controls through impedance changes upon binding phosphorylated α -Syn, achieving an impressive detection limit of 0.237 pg mL^{-1} . A significant achievement of this study was that the sensor was verified by measuring eight different human blood samples, and it could be used as a low-cost immunosensor for the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. Another biomarker of clinical interest is 3-nitrotyrosine (3-NT), associated with oxidative stress conditions. Elevated 3-NT levels serve as early indicators for several disorders, such as cardiovascular diseases, neurodegenerative diseases, and inflammatory conditions. In a biomimetic sensing approach, a molecularly imprinted polydopamine layer was formed on a ZIF-67-modified LIG electrode using L-tyrosine as the template, creating selective binding sites that enabled the specific detection of 3-nitrotyrosine. This advanced sensor employing molecularly imprinted polydopamine integrated on ZIF-67-modified LIG electrodes achieved a detection limit of 6.71 nM; as an application, the sensor was measured using USB-based electrochemical micro-workstation. Sensor was showing one-month long stability, a key step toward reliable long-term monitoring in healthcare settings [59].

Diabetes detection

Monitoring glucose levels is essential for managing diabetes, a globally prevalent metabolic disorder associated with severe complications. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF) Diabetes Atlas 2025, approximately 11.1 % of adults aged 20–79 years, equating to 589 million people, are living with diabetes worldwide. Notably, over 252 million of these individuals are unaware of their condition, increasing their risk of complications [60]. In response, recent advances in electrochemical glucose biosensors have focused on enhancing noninvasiveness, sensitivity, and real-time monitoring using Gr-based materials. Two detection strategies are usually followed: enzymatic platforms typically rely on glucose oxidase immobilized on conductive matrices, often coupled with redox mediators like Prussian blue or phenanthroline derivatives [61–63]. Non-enzymatic sensors utilize redox-active nanoparticles such as NiO [64], Cu_2O [65], Co_3O_4 [66], or bimetallic CuFe_2O_4 [67] to directly catalyze glucose oxidation. Gr materials serve as high-surface-area, conductive scaffolds, including rGO, LSG, Gr sponge, and Gr fiber fabrics [61,68–70]. Among the most advanced systems is a study by Wang et al. which employed a one-step laser-scribed Pt-LSG sensor with

Figure 3

Real-world applications for the detection of NCDs using the Gr-based electrochemical sensor. **(a)** Polydopamine integrated on ZIF-67-modified LIG electrodes for the detection of 3-NT using USB-based microworkstation. Adapted with permission from Elsevier [59]. **(b)** LIG-based sensor with incorporated Fe–Co metal compounds for real-time glucose monitoring from the sweat. Adapted with permission from Elsevier [72]. **(c)** MXene-rGO-based dual-function electrode and real-time monitoring of glucose and pH on the individual's forehead. Adapted with permission from Ref. [44]. Copyright (2024) American Chemical Society.

integrated glucose oxidase and hydroxyethyl cellulose, enabling simultaneous glucose and pH monitoring in human sweat. The sensor demonstrated excellent performance under real exercise conditions, with an LOD of 0.23 μM and reliable correlation to blood glucose levels [69]. Another platform reported by Mwaurah et al. combined Pd–Pt-decorated rGO with a redox mediator and microfluidic neckband architecture. It enabled Bluetooth-based readout, showed strong selectivity over interferences in human sweat, and achieved real-time sweat glucose monitoring during postprandial fluctuations, with an LOD of 46 μM [63]. Despite significant progress in the incorporation of Gr-based materials, several challenges persist, such as validation in real biological fluids, which is still limited; only a subset of studies include serum, sweat, or interstitial fluid analysis (ISF) [44,63,70–72]. Enzymatic sensors are further challenged by pH variability in sweat and ISF. Recent work addresses this issue via integrated pH calibration systems or dual-function sensing modules [44,69] (Figure 2d), setting the stage for future clinically relevant, continuous monitoring platforms to detect diabetes and prevent the burden of NCDs.

Over the past three years, research on sensing technologies for NCDs has increasingly focused on the evaluation of real samples and the integration of wearable devices. Notable progress has been achieved in the monitoring of diabetes and neurological disorders, with sensing platforms advancing toward real-world applications. For diabetes, subcutaneous continuous glucose monitors (CGMs) based on ISF sampling are already commercially available and offer stable multi-week operation without frequent recalibration [73,74]. However, CGMs primarily measure glucose alone; future systems may benefit from simultaneous tracking of additional biomarkers such as insulin, cortisol or epinephrine to enable more comprehensive metabolic profiling [75]. In contrast, developments in the monitoring of cancer and cardiovascular diseases remain comparatively limited, primarily due to the complexity and variability of the associated biomarkers. Among mentioned areas, diabetes monitoring has emerged as the closest to practical implementation, largely because glucose detection in body fluids is relatively straightforward compared to the more complex sensing requirements of other diseases. To overcome the biocompatibility and stability challenges of implantable systems, recent Gr-based research should target minimally invasive platforms such as sweat sensors, which offer enhanced comfort and safety for long-term wearability. The inherent simplicity of glucose as a biomarker, together with ongoing advancements in sensor design, device miniaturization, and non-invasive technologies, has facilitated the development of reliable and user-oriented wearable systems for diabetes management. These platforms may serve as a first step toward complex multi-analyte monitoring, with the potential to surpass

current ISF-based CGMs available on the market. Selected examples are presented in Figure 3.

Conclusion and future outlook

Electrochemical biosensing is an affordable, reliable, and user-friendly technique with a broad application potential in disease prevention and healthcare. However, it faces several challenges commonly associated with interference, stability, and detection limits. Recent advancements have demonstrated that Gr-based materials can effectively address these challenges and push the boundaries. Gr itself can serve as an active material for sensing of crucial biomarkers of NCDs. Nevertheless, recent focus has shifted towards Gr derivatives rather than pristine Gr to overcome limitations related to restacking and agglomeration in biological media. Gr-derived nanomaterials, such as GQDs, rGO, LSG or N-doped Gr, have emerged as even more promising materials for detecting relevant biomarkers. Recent efforts toward upscaling and standardization of Gr-derivatives synthesis, together with tunability of Gr properties by functionalization, paved the way toward new electrode materials that can be effectively applied in this field of research.

Analysis of clinical samples using electrochemical methods continues to pose an important challenge in this field. Recent advancements in the detection of major biomarkers of various NCDs in real samples have also demonstrated substantial progress in this area. The selective biorecognition unit plays a pivotal role in this field, as its specificity is an indispensable prerequisite for developing selective sensors with minimal interference. Detection of relevant biomarkers of NCDs, especially for cancer, cardiovascular diseases, and neurological disorders, from different biological fluids like sweat, serum, and saliva is still limited. Diabetes sensors are well-established in the market; however, for continuous monitoring of glucose and hemoglobin A1C (HbA1C) biomarker, maintaining proper pH remains a limitation, and this should be the future research direction. One of the significant challenges in biomarker detection is the reduction of sample size, especially when the detection limit of the biomarker in the specific fluid is low. Recent attention has been directed towards advancing the detection limit of target biomarkers while simultaneously reducing the sample volume. A viable strategy to address this challenge involves combining lateral flow with electrochemical biosensing. Another promising approach involves exploring emerging printing technologies including, e. g., material inkjet printing, which can lead to precise electrode surface modifications. Research in this field should focus on developing electrochemically active inks, printing technologies for biosensors, and high-precision, low-cost, and low-material-loss printing technologies.

Although Gr-based electrochemical biosensors demonstrated strong performance in laboratory settings, significant challenges remain before their wide translation into commercially viable products for NCDs detection. The majority of reported technologies are still at the proof-of-concept or early prototype validation stage, corresponding to Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) 3–5 [76]. Only a few platforms such as continuous glucose monitoring systems have advanced to higher TRLs and entered the market [77,78]. Scalable and reproducible material synthesis, integration with flexible electronics, user-centered design, and thorough clinical validation represent critical factors to bridge the gap between laboratory research and real-world application. Undoubtedly, the Gr-based electrochemical biosensors have the potential to mature into practical tools for NCDs monitoring and ultimately contribute to improved global health outcomes. This development should be supported by advancing scalable manufacturing processes for the production of standardized Gr-based materials with high batch-to-batch consistency.

Author contribution

T.B.: conceptualization; writing – original draft; writing – review & editing; visualization; M.-A.N.: writing – original draft; writing – review & editing; visualization; I.D.: writing – original draft; writing – review & editing; visualization; P.J.: writing – review & editing; visualization; funding acquisition; D.P.: writing – review & editing; visualization; M.O.: conceptualization; methodology; writing – review & editing; funding acquisition; supervision.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work, the authors used AI to improve the readability and language of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors carefully reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: MO has share in ATOM-IVER (Czechia) and InSiliBio (France) companies. Other authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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- * of special interest
- ** of outstanding interest

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